

2,2' Dipyridyl and 1, 10-Phenanthroline Derivatives of Tribromonitrosorhenium (II)

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In continuation with our previous communication¹, this note is to announce the isolation and study of several nitroso-diimine complexes of rhenium.

The addition of 2,2'-dipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline hydrobromide to a concentrated hydrobromic acid solution of $H_2ReBr_5(NO)$ afforded sparingly soluble salts of the corresponding diimines viz., $dipyH_2[ReBr_5(NO)]$ and $phenH_2[ReBr_5(NO)]$. These were purified through recrystallisation from aqueous hydrobromic acid. The non-electrolytic derivatives viz., $[ReBr_3(dipy)(NO)]$ and $[ReBr_3(phen)(NO)]$ were directly prepared by heating mono 2,2'-dipyridyl (200°) or 1,10-phenanthroline (230°) salts of H_2ReBr_5 in dry nitric oxide. These compounds were also formed by heating the corresponding diimine salts of $H_2ReBr_5(NO)$ around 240° in an inert atmosphere. The reactions took place quantitatively as follows,

Fusion of the non-electrolytes with diimines produced the cationic bis-diimino complexes which gave insoluble chloroplatinates of composition, $[ReBr(dipy)_2(NO)]PtCl_6$ and $[ReBr(phen)_2(NO)]PtCl_6$.

Typical characteristics of a few compounds are shown below.

	Colour	Re%	Br%	NO stretching frequency, cm^{-1}
$dipyH_2[ReBr_5(NO)]$	snuff brown	24.7(24.1)	50.0(51.7)	1715
$phenH_2[ReBr_5(NO)]$	red brown	22.5(23.3)	49.0(50.1)	1725
$[ReBr_3(dipy)(NO)]$	chocolate	30.9(30.4)	39.0(39.2)	1745
$[ReBr_3(phen)(NO)]$	chocolate	29.9(29.3)	38.0(37.7)	1760

The figures in parenthesis are the calculated percentages.

The anionic complexes are quite stable in the solid state and are soluble in dil. aqueous hydrobromic acid, ethanol, acetone etc. The solutions are indefinitely stable in presence of free HBr. The non-electrolytes are insoluble in water and ethanol but are slightly soluble in acetone and freely in dimethylformamide.

All these compounds are weakly paramagnetic at room temperature.

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